

Supplemental material for

Toward sound localization testing in virtual reality to aid in the screening of auditory processing disorders

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1. Additional tables and figures

n	G	Age	Left ear							Right ear						
			<i>f</i> (Hz)	125	250	500	1k	2k	4k	8k	<i>f</i> (Hz)	125	250	500	1k	2k
			HL (dB)							HL (dB)						
1	F	28	10	0	0	0	10	10	5	10	0	0	5	10	5	5
2	F	26	-5	10	5	0	10	5	5	15	0	0	5	20	10	0
3	M	21	5	5	5	0	5	5	0	10	10	0	0	-5	15	5
4	M	29	0	5	10	5	0	10	15	10	10	5	5	5	15	10
5	M	24	10	0	0	5	15	10	5	5	0	-5	5	5	15	5
6	M	26	5	5	5	0	-5	5	-5	5	5	5	0	-5	0	0
7	M	31	5	0	5	10	20	20	10	5	0	5	5	10	5	-10
8	M	25	5	0	0	5	0	10	-10	5	0	0	5	0	5	0
9	M	51	10	0	5	5	10	10	10	15	5	0	5	15	5	5
10	M	24	5	0	-5	-5	0	0	-5	5	-5	-5	5	10	5	-5
11	M	27	5	5	0	5	10	5	-5	5	0	-5	5	15	5	0
12	M	26	5	0	-5	10	10	-5	0	5	-5	-5	5	5	-5	-5
13	M	29	10	10	0	5	0	5	25	10	5	-5	0	0	15	0
14	M	23	0	15	5	5	-5	10	-5	5	0	0	5	0	10	0
15	M	35	0	-5	-5	0	0	20	-5	5	0	0	10	0	20	-10
16	F	30	0	0	0	0	10	5	0	-5	-5	-5	0	-10	-10	10
17	M	24	0	0	0	0	0	5	-5	0	-5	0	0	-5	0	0
18	F	27	5	10	15	10	15	10	-10	15	10	10	10	15	5	-5
19	M	26	5	5	0	-5	5	-10	-10	5	0	0	5	5	0	0
20	M	26	15	10	-10	-5	0	5	0	15	15	10	15	20	15	5

Table S 1. Study participants' demographic details and individual pure tone audiogram results for both ears.

Figure S 1. Technical drawing of the semicircular loudspeaker array used in the experiment (top view). It includes the 3D printed holders for the individual LED dots (Kai Altwiker, TH Köln).

Figure S 2. Frontal view of the semicircular loudspeaker array built for the experiment (Kai Altwiker, TH Köln).

Figure S 3. Zoom in on a lateral view of the loudspeaker array. Individual 3D-printed cases hold each digitally controlled LED pixel (Kai Altwiker, TH Köln).

Figure S 4. Histograms of the RMS localization errors for the three test conditions (C1, C2, C3) with normal distribution fit (solid black line). The optimal width and number of bins for each histogram was calculated according to the Freedman-Diaconis rule. Lilliefors tests for normality revealed no violation of normality for any condition.

Figure S 5. Quantile-Quantile (QQ) plots for the three test conditions (C1, C2, C3) showing the empirically observed quantiles of the RMS localization error (ordinate) as a function of the condition-specific fitted normal distribution (abscissa). Lilliefors tests for normality revealed no violation of normality for any condition.

Figure S 6. Subjective localization of a sound source as a function of its position over the horizontal plane. The graph shows the objective position (abscissa) and the corresponding subjective localization (ordinate) of each subject in all the experimental scenarios (C1, C2, and C3). The solid lines are the fifth-order best-fit polynomial curves for the discrete data. The solid black line represents the ideal correct localization, and the dotted gray lines represent the closest adjacent positions to both the left and right sides of the ideal correct localization.

Figure S 7. RMS localization errors for the three test conditions (C1, C2, C3) as a function of four epochs, with epoch 1 containing trials 1-9, epoch 2 containing trials 10-19, epoch 3 containing trials 19-27, and epoch 4 containing trials 28-37.

Figure S 8. Picture gallery. The sound localization test in VR is available in different virtual worlds.

2. Video material

The video **Video S1_Setup.mp4** illustrates the setup of the loudspeaker array used in the study, including all the parts required for its construction, i.e., microphone stands, Genelec 8020D loudspeakers, 3D printed parts (loudspeaker holders, LED holders, and connectors), the strand of Adafruit WS2801 pixels and the acoustically transparent curtain.

The video **Video S2_C1_3Trials.mp4** illustrates three trials of the sound localization procedure in the first test condition (C1). The subject uses a modified Oculus Quest 2 controller to indicate the location of the perceived sound object in the space relative to their self-body axes. They receive visual feedback on the direction they are pointing as the LED dot changes its color.

The video **Video S3_C3_3Trials.mp4** illustrates three trials taken from a screen capture of the VR condition (C3). A child-appropriate, gamified, and entirely automated sound localization test based on the ERKI method was developed. It runs on a standalone head-mounted display (Oculus Quest 2).

3. Data files

Table S1_Data_Demographics and Audiograms.xls contains the raw data from the study participants' demographic information and their pure tone audiogram results.

Blueprint S2_Setup.pdf contains the blueprint of the loudspeaker array setup.

Table S2_Data_Experimental raw data.xls contains the raw experimental data from all test conditions (C1, C2, and C3) and all participants included in the analysis (n=19).